

HISTORICAL-CRITICAL PEDAGOGY AND THE INTERNATIONALIZATION OF THE NATURAL SCIENCES CURRICULUM: A LOOK AT TEACHER TRAINING

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ABSTRACT

This article proposes a discussion on Historical-Critical Pedagogy supported by the internationalization of the natural sciences curriculum as an instrument to enhance scientific production. In this way, it aims to highlight the knowledge of teachers in that area in relation to the internationalization process, using the aforementioned pedagogy as a pillar in the construction of the proposed reflections. The methodological path of this work is based on the aforementioned pedagogy aligned with the case study, presenting a quantitative-qualitative approach. Regarding the data analysis method, document analysis was used. From the application of the questionnaire, it was evident that teachers develop a pedagogical practice based on problem solving based on themes linked to global citizenship, virtual education, cultural diversity among other themes which, aligned with Historical-Critical Pedagogy, acts as an instrument that strengthens scientific knowledge and social transformation.

Keywords: Natural Sciences, Internationalization of the Curriculum, Historical-Critical Pedagogy, Teacher Training.

1 INTRODUCTION

In view of the demands of contemporary education and the expansion of the planetary process (Knight, 2020), reflecting on the role of teaching natural sciences has become a necessity, since the growing scientific and technological dissemination supported by the promotion of learning. In fact, study plans are fundamental mechanisms in the development of educational tools, finding in Historical-Critical Pedagogy the foundation for the formation of protagonist students, committed to social reality.

This construction enables the development of educational practices in science that culminate in the development of research and projects based on a diversified curriculum in connection with the needs of society (Cachapuz *et al.*, 2005).

In this regard, knowledge in natural sciences aims to help students understand the natural space, as well as encourage them to preserve the environment through the creation of environmental conservation mechanisms (Chassot, 2003).

According to Cachapuz *et al.* (2005), we are faced with the need for curricular renewal in science teaching through reflective pedagogical practice. In fact, the formation of active subjects involves the promotion of the curriculum, using problem situations to motivate intellectual autonomy through the encouragement of scientific education.

Research shows that the teaching of natural sciences based on the appropriation of Historical-Critical Pedagogy is still widespread today, indicating the lack of books that can align with the aforementioned pedagogical practice (Massi *et al.*, 2019 *apud* Stadler; Marques; Lambach, 2024).

Recognition of the growing importance attributed to science education requires careful study of how to achieve this goal. In this construction process, higher education plays a leading role in the development of academic research in the teaching of natural sciences in connection with educational needs.

In line with the idea presented, Knight (2020) argues that the Internationalization of Higher Education has been constantly expanding, which has impacted the curriculum, promoting reflections on terms such as “global citizenship”, “development of global skills”, “international education”, “interculturality”, “academic mobility”, among other terms, becoming an object of reflection by the scientific community.

In line with the expansion of internationalization and globalization in Higher Education Institutions (HEIs), Historical-Critical Pedagogy motivates teachers and education researchers to reflect on what type of curriculum is being promoted in HEIs and how this construction is reaching basic education.

“Historical-Critical Pedagogy is a pedagogical practice that aims to work with systematized knowledge, transforming it into meaningful knowledge so that, in the process of transmission and assimilation, the student is able to make connections [...]” (Jesus; Santos; Andrade, 2019, p. 72). In this regard, the importance of contextual reality is considered, combined with interdisciplinary work in defense of pedagogical practices committed to social reality and systematized knowledge.

In this dialogue, Goodson (2012) encourages us to reflect on the importance of the curriculum and its implications in the epistemological and ontological construction of knowledge. Saviani (2014), seeking to understand the meaning of education and the curriculum, found that the autonomy of the educational space is the key to the autonomy of education, developed in a systematic and elaborate way. In fact, the valorization of the school in the face of the multiplicity of educational modalities ensures the full development of the elaborated knowledge. Thus, this work aims to discuss the curriculum and its internationalization process aligned with Historical-Critical Pedagogy, culminating in the discursive meaning of natural science teachers in the aforementioned construction process.

2 THEORETICAL FRAMEWORK

The curriculum is a key theme in the teaching-learning process (Goodson, 2012). Thinking of the curriculum as an instrument in the promotion of knowledge encourages us to look at it as a motivator for social change.

In fact, the curriculum taught at HEIs is geared towards training reflective students who, in the face of teaching, use their pedagogical practice as a means of empowerment to exercise global citizenship. In this process of development, teachers and researchers in education are faced with the rapid expansion of the internationalization process, which has impacted the curriculum and the way content is taught in the classroom.

From the epistemological approach, the discipline is personified as a scientific construction that converges towards each of the branches of knowledge, with its own characteristics obtained through an analytical method aligned with reality, producing a deepening of knowledge (Luck, 2013).

Historically, the relationship between the curriculum and educational actions was surrounded by debates that sought to expand the possibilities of their pedagogical action. Thus, the potential issue that mobilizes the aforementioned reflection is precisely the increasingly greater dimension of globalization and its effects on education and, more specifically, on learning.

In accordance with the idea presented, Leask (2015) envisions the curriculum from a global perspective, encompassing regional and local levels, culminating in the student's education based on aspects such as professional development and citizenship training, participation in research groups and dialogue between disciplines, and this process is surrounded by paradigms that need to be overcome.

Thinking about the training of natural science teachers from the perspective of internationalization allows us to understand that the curriculum, combined with scientific developments, broadens our view of its importance in promoting the common good.

When Leask (2015) asks the question “*what is internationalization?*”, the researcher points to the importance of internationalization in the development of global education, highlighting it as a strategic action.

For Knight (2020), the Internationalization of Higher Education is a process that integrates the international, intercultural and global dimensions of knowledge, whose purpose emerges in the offering of academic disciplines, enabling the approach of complex themes that involve policies and study programs in response to global needs.

In this regard, comprehensive internationalization is defined by Beneitone (2019) as a commitment that is made through actions whose objective is to disseminate the perspective of teaching, research and extension in HEIs. Thus, the training of natural science teachers from the perspective of internationalization enables the training of reflective professionals, which is the main objective of Historical-Critical Pedagogy.

Saviani used Historical-Critical Pedagogy to promote a pedagogical proposal applied to a dialectical concept of education that is determined by factors internal and external to the educational environment, as well as the social formation of the student with a view to overcoming the historical-dialectical paradigm (Jesus; Santos; Andrade, 2019).

In effect, thinking of Historical-Critical Pedagogy as an ideological field that reproduces everyday situations linked to scientific and technological production makes natural sciences an emerging field that enables the transformation of social reality, redirecting the focus of systematized knowledge to educational practice as a social movement.

Historical-Critical Pedagogy has Demerval Saviani as a great reference as a teacher and researcher. Based on considerations about the teaching-learning process, it is observed that the aforementioned pedagogy constitutes an indissoluble unit that seeks to promote reflections on education and work.

Sociability and communicability in teaching work make Historical-Critical Pedagogy a methodology whose educational work deliberates on producing knowledge in a direct and intentional way with the singular perception that this construction is done in a historical and collective way (Saviani, 2011 *apud* Jesus; Santos; Andrade, 2019).

Historical-Critical Pedagogy, as a didactic perspective for teaching, has its starting point in social reality, converging towards elaborated knowledge and systematized knowledge. In

this path, Saviani proposes overcoming common sense, prioritizing scientific knowledge as a way of transforming reality (Ramos, 2012).

Combined with the reflection on the epistemological stance of Historical-Critical Pedagogy, the renewal of natural science teaching arises from the need to overcome curricular fragmentation, through which, for a long time, science was seen as elitist and decontextualized from social reality (Cachapuz *et. al.*, 2005).

Science teaching is meant to raise questions that enable students to proceed correctly in specific situations. [...] It is clear that Critical Historical Pedagogy (CHP) must provide paths between the knowledge developed and its acquisition in future generations (Jabur; França; Jabur, 2021, p. 322-323).

For Saviani (2012) cited by Jabur, França and Jabur (2021), there is the possibility of using education as an instrument of social advancement and, in this process, the teaching of natural sciences captures the historical and cultural aspects that enable the direction towards the scientific training of new generations.

In effect, teaching natural sciences emerges as an empowering instrument for students, promoting pedagogical work based on problem situations, where students are led to reflect, plan, experiment and evaluate.

In these terms, the book *The Necessary Renewal of Science Teaching* (Cachapuz, *et. al.*, 2005) allows us to expand our reflections on the natural science curriculum that has been worked on within universities, showing the importance of scientific literacy.

Still according to Cachapuz *et. al.* (2005), the renewal of science teaching is aligned with the epistemological renewal of teaching through initial teacher training based on research, whose spectrum focuses on the elaboration of projects and research that enable experimentation.

In this sense, thinking about the alignment between Historical-Critical Pedagogy and the renewal of natural science teaching allows us to build an education aligned with contemporary needs, where the aforementioned process is soaked in actions aligned with the expansion of globalization, acting as a catalyst for the internationalization process.

Historical-Critical Pedagogy outlines the basic structure for teaching natural sciences based on the need for adequate time and space alongside practical classes in the area in question (Saviani, 2012 *apud* Jabur; França; Jabur, 2021).

In the requirement, practices in science, it has been noted that the practical method obtains better results when it comes to learning science, as it shows science as a discovery, explains certain knowledge to students, having them

as active participants in their classes and not just spectators (Jabur; França; Jabur, 2021, p. 326).

In this regard, the vision of the United Nations Educational, Scientific and Cultural Organization (UNESCO) on the need for scientific and inclusive education stands out, in order to ensure learning opportunities, outlining the guidelines for global education (Saviani, 2011 *apud* Haddad; Pereira, 2013).

According to Haddad and Pereira (2013), pedagogical work from the perspective of humanization seeks to develop human potential, an inseparable aspect of the ability to construct knowledge and characterize it based on human experiences and, in this construction, the teaching of natural sciences has become an important actor, strengthening collaboration with the education sectors.

Thinking about teaching natural sciences, characterizing it as an interdisciplinary act based on the search for boldness, allows the promotion of research, finding in academic spaces the place that enhances scientific literacy. For Chassot (2003), scientific literacy constitutes an emerging line of science didactics and, in this dialogue, Leask (2021) proposes the global literacy model that includes international and intercultural capabilities that incline and enable students to act in social reality.

According to Chassot (2003), the promotion of natural science teaching must include a curriculum that is guided by the social and personal experiences of students. Designing an education with equity involves the reworking of knowledge, aiming at the didactic transposition of content.

Understanding science also makes it easier for us to contribute to controlling and predicting the transformations that occur in nature. Thus, we will be able to propose these transformations so that they lead to a better quality of life (Chassot, 2003, p. 91).

In effect, educational work seeks to convert objective knowledge into school knowledge, implying the definition and production of the pedagogical project as a guiding work in the selection of content that will make up the Curricular Pedagogical Proposal (Haddad; Pereira, 2013).

Thus, for Historical-Critical Pedagogy, education has the purpose of work, whose materiality is the objective knowledge produced historically (Saviani, 2000 *apud* Ramos, 2012). Therefore, the educational space has the role of enabling methodical, scientific knowledge and, in this context, the renewal of the teaching of natural sciences permeates all these dimensions,

culminating in the best preparation of students for their performance in the social and professional reality.

3 METHODOLOGY

The methodology of an article outlines the procedures used to conduct the research, including the type of study, sample selection, data collection and analysis methods, ethical considerations, and study limitations. A detailed and transparent description is essential to ensure the replicability and reliability of the results, as well as to provide a solid basis for the interpretation and generalization of the findings.

The methodological approach of this work is based on Historical-Critical Pedagogy, constituting itself as a methodology whose educational practice deliberates on producing knowledge in a direct and intentional way (Saviani, 2011 *apud* Jesus; Santos; Andrade, 2019). In dialogue with the aforementioned pedagogy, there is the use of the case study which, according to Yin (2001), is a study based on situations related to social reality.

Regarding the research subjects, they are teachers in the area of natural sciences who work in basic education. Regarding the research technique, a questionnaire was used to obtain information from the empirical field.

The questionnaire is defined as a “[...] research technique for obtaining results in social research [...]” (Gil, 1987, p. 124). The questionnaire was made available online, via *Google Forms*, presenting open and closed questions, which allowed us to generate graphs that are available in the presentation of the results.

Regarding the questions asked to teachers about the curriculum and its internationalization process aligned with the renewal of natural science teaching from the perspective of Historical-Critical Pedagogy, we have:

- 1) Dear participant, have you heard about the proposal for curricular renewal in the teaching of natural sciences?
- 2) Dear participant, comment on the proposal for curricular renewal of natural science teaching combined with Historical-Critical Pedagogy;
- 3) Dear participant, have you heard about the internationalization of the natural sciences curriculum?
- 4) Dear participant, during your initial training, did you have information about the internationalization process of the natural sciences curriculum?

- 5) Dear participant, comment on how the internationalization of the natural sciences curriculum is supported by Historical-Critical Pedagogy in promoting scientific education.

This research has a mixed approach, characterized as quantitative and qualitative. The quantitative approach is characterized by the quantification of data or information that can be expressed in absolute numbers or percentages based on the research findings (Triviños, 1987). The qualitative approach is characterized by knowledge or contact with the direct source of data, by its descriptive and observational nature of the meanings that people give to things (Neves, 1996).

According to Minayo (2013), the qualitative research method is understood as one that deals with the subjective level of social reality, treated through the history, values and attitudes of social actors and, in this research, educational actors. The results obtained are presented below, as well as the aforementioned discussions.

Regarding the type of analysis, documentary analysis was used, which consists of a set of operations that aim to analyze the content of a document or speech in order to extract information that can reference its consultation and/or citation in cases of theoretical foundation (Bardin, 1977).

4 RESULTS AND DISCUSSIONS

This section is intended to present the results found from the application of the questionnaire. 111 teachers in the area of natural sciences who work in basic education participated in the research.

Regarding the question about whether they had heard about the proposed curriculum renewal for teaching natural sciences, 100% of participants responded yes, indicating that educators are aligned with contemporary educational needs.

In this context, thinking about the teaching of natural sciences based on Freire (1996) allows us to reflect on the need for an emancipatory education that gives human beings the opportunity to intervene in the world, so as to be capable of great actions in favor of the common good.

In this dialogue, Chassot (2003) highlights ways to renew the teaching of natural sciences based on scientific literacy and the need to work on content based on problem situations that motivate students to think of viable solutions to the problems that arise in today's society.

Questioning, together with observation and investigation, is a fundamental aspect of developing students' understanding of the world [...]. This configuration will make the subject feel close to being able to transform the world, being more participatory, thus contributing to the understanding of the diverse ways of using natural resources and understanding the possibility of the subject's emancipation (Jabur; França; Jabur, 2021, p. 327).

Regarding the question about the proposed curricular renewal of natural science teaching combined with Historical-Critical Pedagogy, it was observed that educators believe that the use of said pedagogy as a teaching methodology makes it possible to think of students as reflective beings, active in the social context in which they are immersed, making use of experimental practices to reflect and change reality from a sustainable perspective.

In relation to Historical-Critical Pedagogy, it is observed that:

Once again, this Pedagogy establishes how essential school is for society, how relevant it is not only in the present and in the past, but also in the future for new generations. This means that it is not only necessary, it becomes indisputable. This is because we had access to systematized knowledge in the past, and we have it in the present. We cannot deprive new generations of having it in the future (Ramos, 2012, p. 5).

Next, teachers were asked if they had ever heard about the internationalization of the natural sciences curriculum and 57.9% of teachers said they had not (Graph 1), highlighting the need for dialogues on the topic in HEIs, since globalization is immersed in the teaching process, impacting learning in the formation of the social being.

In line with the teachers' response, Beneitone (2019) argues that in most Latin American countries, reforms of their higher education systems have been promoted in order to consolidate educational growth with equity, promoting improvements in the quality of teaching and the need to adapt academic and professional profiles to the new needs of a global world.

Chart 1 - Dear participant, have you heard about Curriculum Internationalization?

Source: Prepared by the author (2024).

Next, when teachers were asked whether they had received information about the internationalization process of the natural sciences curriculum during their initial training, 92.1% of participants responded that they had not (Graph 2). In this regard, it was observed that teachers in this area, although they did not have courses that addressed the topic in question, worked in the classroom on topics related to global citizenship, virtual education, cultural diversity, globalization, technology production, and the use and disposal of chemical products, which are topics that emerged from the internationalization process.

Graph 2 - Dear participant, during your initial training, did you have information about the internationalization process of the natural sciences curriculum?

Source: Prepared by the author (2024).

Given this finding, the need to think about the curriculum from the perspective of internationalization becomes evident, since 21st century education is immersed in the extensive process of globalization which, supported by Historical-Critical Pedagogy, culminates in the formation of the social being as a global citizen.

Finally, educators were asked to comment on how the internationalization of the natural science curriculum is supported by Historical-Critical Pedagogy in promoting scientific education and, in response, teachers reported that the aforementioned area is soaked in pedagogical and experimental practices for understanding reality.

In this construction process, it is observed that scientific literacy, also known as scientific literacy, constitutes a factor of social inclusion, enabling students to understand science as the language in which nature is written (Chassot, 2003).

In effect, interdisciplinary work emerges as an instrument capable of contextualizing content to the reality of students, enhancing work based on solving problem situations, creating viable solutions (Lima; Alves, 2022).

Leask (2021) advises that creating a dynamic, intercultural and global learning community in the classroom often requires teachers and students to leave their “comfort zone”, enabling interdisciplinary, contextualized work committed to social responsibility.

In light of such reflections, it is clear that human solidarity is the fruit of socialization process, states Seffner (2016), with education being the space for this construction through the development of solidarity regimes, providing equality and respect for diversity.

In fact, the need for curricular renewal in the teaching of natural sciences based on Historical-Critical Pedagogy should prioritize quality scientific education for the entire population. Using pedagogical planning as a tool in its promotion is to contribute to the best preparation of students, acting on the pillars of teaching, research and extension.

5 CONCLUSION

During this work, a dialogue was held between Historical-Critical Pedagogy aligned with the process of internationalization of the curriculum, culminating in reflections on the need to renew the teaching of natural sciences. It was evident that teachers in this area, although they have not had the opportunity to deepen theoretical knowledge about the internationalization of the natural sciences curriculum, develop a pedagogical praxis based on problem-solving based on themes linked to global citizenship, virtual education, cultural diversity, globalization and technology production.

In this context, Historical-Critical Pedagogy emerges as an instrument that enhances the production of scientific knowledge. Using this pedagogy to promote the teaching of natural sciences converges with the teaching-learning process, whose materiality is the objective knowledge produced historically.

In this regard, working on Historical-Critical Pedagogy from the perspective of scientific literacy culminates in the reflection on the educational space as a promoter of methodical and scientific knowledge and, consequently, the glimpse of the renewal of the teaching of natural sciences that impacts on the better preparation of students for their performance in social and professional reality.

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